

Rice-based cropping systems

Potential for increased rice Production in some rainfed areas of Bangladesh

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One of the most common and important rainfed cropping patterns in Bangladesh is aus rice (sown in Mar.–Apr. and harvested in July–Aug.) followed by transplanted aman rice (transplanted in July–Aug. and harvested in Nov.–Dec.). The pattern of monsoon rainfall is typically unimodal in Bangladesh. In the double-cropping system, most farmers grow two local rice varieties, but some grow one local and one high yielding variety. Farmers in some areas have recently begun to grow two crops of high yielding varieties under rainfed conditions, but average production is usually low.

Four new rice cropping patterns were designed and compared with four existing patterns under rainfed conditions in farmers' fields in the BRR I Pilot Project Area. Farmers generally applied

higher management to the modern than to the local varieties, particularly in terms of fertilizer application, weeding, and insect control. The patterns were replicated in individual farmers' fields and the grain yield was determined by crop cutting. The highest yield was from two crops of modern varieties, BR3 followed by BR4 (see figure).

Productivity and management of farmers' aus rice crops on a rainfed double-cropped area of Bangladesh

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During the 1975 and 1976 aus seasons, crop-cut studies were conducted in farmers' fields in the BRR I project area where two crops of rainfed rice per year are grown. The first aus crop is either direct seeded or transplanted in April or

May and harvested from late July to early September. It is followed by a transplanted aman crop. Samples of 5 sq m were taken from farmers' aus crops that were being harvested. Each sample was threshed, cleaned, and weighed, and moisture content was determined in the field. To ascertain the level of crop management used in each plot, each farmer was interviewed, a one-page questionnaire serving as an interview guide.

The productivity of the high yielding varieties (HYV) was significantly higher than that of the local varieties in both years (see table); however, variability among samples was large. The local varieties had significantly shorter growth duration than the HYV; that is probably the most important character influencing farmers' choice of varieties. The following transplanted aman crop must be planted as early as possible after the aus crop to maintain high yields and escape cold injury during flowering. This also explains why the long-duration, high yielding aus and aman varieties are transplanted earlier than the local short-duration aus varieties. The local photosensitive aman varieties can be transplanted later because they flower

Data on average productivity and farm management collected by crop cuts in the 1975 and 1976 aus seasons, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

Annual production of eight double-cropped rice patterns under rainfed conditions, Bangladesh.

Factor	1975		1976	
	HYV ^a	Local ^b	HYV ^a	Local ^b
Samples (no.)	40	11	73	93
Yield (t/ha)	3.6	1.8	3.1	1.6
Yield range (t/ha)	1.4–5.2	1.0–3.6	1.7–4.8	1.0–2.2
Field duration (days)	96	72	92	[89] 71 ^c
Direct seeded ^d	–	–	4	80
Plowings (no.)	5.4	5.1	5.1	4.9
Harrowings (no.)	5.5	4.6	6.2	5.8
Date (seeded) transplanted	May 29	Jun 12	May 22	(Apr 24) Jun 9
Seedling age (days)	33	23	32	32
Farmers using N-P-K (%)	87-60-5	55-45-0	92-64-16	80-48-3
Rate of fertilization (kg N-P ₂ O ₅ -K ₂ O/ha)	51-44-20	28-38-0	53-41-34	37-46-36
Farmers that did not weed (%)	10	27	2	51
Farmers that weeded once (%)	24	64	39	53
Farmers that weeded twice (%)	46	9	54	16
Farmers that weeded thrice (%)	20	0	5	0
Farmers that used pesticide (%)	32	0	32	5
Monthly rainfall (cm)	May 35.1	Jun 22.1	May 27.4	Jun 52.1

^aHigh yielding varieties (HYV) were Chandina and IR8.

^bThe local variety was Pukhi.

^cThe figure in brackets is for direct-seeded samples.

^dBecause of a late start, no direct-seeded local samples were harvested in 1975.

Announcement

When the first edition of *Standard Evaluation System for Rice* was printed in 1975, it was agreed that the system would be updated after several years of use. The world's rice scientists rapidly and widely adopted the standard scoring system and are now making recommendations to the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) for its improvement.

The IRTP plans to print the second edition of the *Standard Evaluation System for Rice* during 1978. Each scientist who has used the system is encouraged to make recommendations for improving the scales of particular traits. Suggestions received by April 15, 1978 will be discussed by participants at the International Rice Research Conference in April 1978; the revised publication will be printed about June 1978.

Submit recommendations to: International Rice Testing Program, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

before the cold nights begin, but they yield lower because their vegetative phase is shorter. The local aus varieties are better adapted to direct seeding; farmers plant them early to extend the growing season.

Farmers generally gave higher levels of productivity in 1975 was about 15% management to the HYV than to the local higher than in 1976. The rainfall pattern rices. More farmers applied higher rates of during grain filling probably explains the fertilizers at more balanced doses to the difference. ~~W~~ HYV and weeded them more often than they did the local rices. The average

IR26 does well as gogorancah crop in Indonesia

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Gogorancah is the direct seeding of rice on moist aerobic soil. From 30 to 40 days after seeding, the fields are banded and allowed to flood. Farmers along the north coastal plain of Java have extensively followed this culture for years.

Seven lowland rice varieties were tested on farmers' fields near Indramayu, West Java, to determine their yield potential when grown under gogorancah culture at the beginning of the wet

Varietal testing for gogorancah rice culture. Cropping systems research, Indramayu, Indonesia, 1975-76.

Variety	Maturity (DS) ^a	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Daily production (kg/ha)
IR28	105	95	4.4	42.4
B-9C	110	96	3.6	32.1
IR30	110	95	3.8	34.2
C4-63G	125	115	5.6	44.6
IR26	125	101	5.9	47.0
IR34	135	137	3.1	23.2
Pelita I/1	140	141	5.2	37.2

^aDays after sowing in seedbed or direct seeding in field.

season. Pelita I/1 was used as a check.

IR26 yielded the highest (5.9 t/ha), closely followed by C4-63G (5.6 t/ha) and Pelita I/1 (5.2 t/ha) (see table). IR28 harvest 15 days earlier and produce and other less known varieties yielded higher yields than those who grow considerably less. In terms of production per day IR26 was first (47.0 kg/day) followed by C4-63G (44.6 kg/day) and IR28 (42.4 kg/day).

Pelita I/1 produced only 37.2 kg/day.

IR26 appears to be very suitable for gogorancah. Farmers who use IR26 can and Pelita I/1 (5.2 t/ha) (see table). IR28 harvest 15 days earlier and produce and other less known varieties yielded higher yields than those who grow considerably less. In terms of production per day IR26 was first (47.0 kg/day) followed by C4-63G (44.6 kg/day) and IR28 (42.4 kg/day). Furthermore, IR26 is tolerant of Pelita I/1. Furthermore, IR26 is tolerant of the brown planthopper, a serious pest of the Indramayu area. ~~W~~

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Stamp